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*Poems,
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and Others*

OWL

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I ran to a dark, narrow road
Insane night with the flickering lights
I saw an owl, strong and vigilant
Yet, wondering without an owner

Escaped a murky route
I thought I was free
An owl followed without hesitation
Once again, a somber covered the way

Groove fitted the path
I fought, sturdy mind, vehement hull
It lasted decades, vast peril
Risky hallway, and yet the owl was no longer there

The hunted owl vanished
Never seen again
Perhaps, a hard-fought battle
That neither I nor, think I can escape with